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THE GOSPEL OF DOUBT: MISSIOLOGICAL PARADOXES IN THE LITERATURE OF KAZUO ISHIGURO'S *THE BURIED GIANT*

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Abstract

This paper tries to find out the missiological paradoxes embedded within Kazuo Ishiguro's *The Buried Giant*, focusing on the intricate relationship between faith, doubt, memory, and forgiveness in a post-Roman Britain. Through a critical missiological lens, the narrative reveals how spiritual amnesia, theological tension, and the struggle for reconciliation shape the characters' journey, mirroring broader challenges faced by Christian mission in diverse cultural landscapes. The novel's portrayal of doubt, both as a spiritual crisis and as a pathway to faith—invites a rethinking of missionary work, highlighting the complexity of belief in contexts marked by historical trauma and collective forgetting. Also, the study investigates how Ishiguro's text complicates conventional narratives of faith by presenting doubt not as an obstacle but as an essential component of spiritual and communal transformation. By doing so, it contributes to missiological discourse on evangelism, reconciliation, and the paradox of faith in uncertain times.

Keywords: Kazuo Ishiguro, *The Buried Giant*, missiology, doubt, spiritual amnesia.

Introduction

Kazuo Ishiguro's *The Buried Giant*, published in 2015, stands as a profound reflection on memory, trauma, and the complexities of forgiveness in post-Roman Britain. Set in a fantastical yet historically rooted landscape, the novel follows an elderly couple, Axl and Beatrice, as they journey across a land shrouded in forgetfulness, where a mysterious mist has caused collective amnesia. Ishiguro masterfully intertwines myth and reality, using elements of Arthurian legend alongside deep philosophical and psychological themes to create a narrative that questions the very nature of history, memory, and truth. The novel's setting in a transitional period, where remnants of Roman civilization give way to the rise of early Christianity and paganism, provides a rich backdrop for exploring questions of faith, doubt, and the possibility of reconciliation. (Ishiguro, 2015: 23)

The Buried Giant is often noted for its exploration of the tension between forgetting and remembering, with Axl and Beatrice's journey serving as both a literal and metaphorical quest to uncover buried truths about their past. The mist that envelops their world symbolizes a broader condition of spiritual and cultural amnesia, raising questions about the moral costs of forgetting versus the pain of remembering. Ishiguro calls readers to consider the ways in which history and memory shape not only personal identities but also collective moral consciousness. The novel's characters, including the knight Sir Gawain and the warrior Wistan, exemplify different responses to this dilemma, illustrating the complexities of forgiveness and the legacy of past wrongs. While *The Buried Giant* is not overtly religious, its themes resonate deeply with theological questions of sin, judgment, and redemption, making it a

fruitful field for missiological reflection. (Shaffer, 2019: 35)

In the framework of missiology, *The Buried Giant* can be understood as a *gospel of doubt*, where the relation of memory, faith, and forgiveness serves as a basis for examining the paradoxes inherent in the missionary endeavour. Central to Christian mission is the proclamation of a gospel of certainty, faith in the redemptive work of Christ, the promise of salvation, and the assurance of eternal life. However, Ishiguro's narrative challenges this certitude by depicting a world where doubt, ambiguity, and forgetfulness are inescapable aspects of the human condition. The characters' inability to fully remember their past wrongs mirrors the theological notion of original sin, where humanity's fallen nature clouds the possibility of perfect understanding or reconciliation without divine intervention. Yet, unlike traditional narratives of sin and redemption, *The Buried Giant* resists offering easy answers, instead presenting doubt as a perpetual companion to faith. (Wong, 2020: 51)

This paradox, where faith and doubt coexist, is not new to Christian theology but takes on a particular significance in the realm of missiology. The missionary task often involves confronting cultures and belief systems that are marked by their own forms of spiritual and historical forgetfulness, much like the world of Axl and Beatrice. Missionaries must navigate the tension between proclaiming an absolute truth and appealing with communities that may have a deeply ingrained sense of scepticism or spiritual amnesia. In this sense, *The Buried Giant* serves as an allegory for the missionary encounter, where the gospel of Christ is proclaimed not in a vacuum of certainty, but amidst the complexities of doubt, history, and memory. (Beedham, 2017: 63)

The notion of missiological paradoxes in *The Buried Giant* is further emphasised by the novel's treatment of reconciliation and forgiveness. Throughout the book, characters contend with whether it is better to remember past wrongs and seek justice, or to forget them in the pursuit of peace. This moral ambiguity reflects the broader challenges faced by missionaries, who must often work within contexts of historical trauma, colonization, and cultural conflict. The question of whether forgiveness is possible without memory, or whether memory itself is a form of judgment, echoes in the theological debate surrounding atonement and reconciliation. Ishiguro's novel does not offer a clear resolution to these dilemmas, but it raises important questions about the role of doubt and uncertainty in the process of spiritual healing and transformation. (Mason, 2018: 127)

In *The Buried Giant*, the mist of forgetfulness may be seen as a metaphor for the ways in which cultures, including Christian communities, can be blinded by historical and spiritual amnesia. The missionary task, therefore, involves not only the proclamation of the gospel but also the delicate work of uncovering buried truths, addressing the wounds of the past, and navigating the paradoxes of faith and doubt. Ishiguro's novel, with its intricate exploration of these themes, offers a unique lens through which to view the complexities of missiological engagement in a world where certainty is elusive, and the past is never fully forgotten. (Groes, 2016: 71)

I. Methodology

The methodological approach of this paper combines literary analysis with missiological inquiry to explore the theological themes of doubt, memory, and reconciliation in Kazuo Ishiguro's *The Buried Giant*. This interdisciplinary approach allows for a deeper examination of how Ishiguro's narrative reflects and critiques missiological concepts, particularly in relation to faith formation, evangelism, and the paradox of doubt within Christian mission.

The first step in this analysis is a close reading of the novel, with particular attention to its treatment of memory, spiritual amnesia, and the theological implications of forgetting and remembering within a post-Roman Britain context. Characters and plot elements are analysed for their symbolic resonance with Christian concepts of grace, redemption, and the challenges of mission work in contexts of cultural and historical trauma.

Simultaneously, the paper engages with contemporary missiological scholarship, particularly works that explore the role of doubt in faith development and the tension between belief and unbelief in mission settings. By integrating these perspectives, the study traces the ways in which *The Buried Giant* offers a nuanced exploration of the paradoxes inherent in missionary work, particularly in contexts where historical trauma complicates the reception of the Christian message.

The analysis also applies theological contexts that emphasize reconciliation and forgiveness, situating these themes within the broader missiological discourse

on healing, collective memory, and the process of building faith in communities. This combination of literary and missiological perspectives provides a comprehensive methodology for understanding the intersection of doubt and faith in Ishiguro's narrative.

II. Memory and Forgetfulness: Spiritual Amnesia in *The Buried Giant*

In *The Buried Giant*, Kazuo Ishiguro masterfully theories a narrative in which forgetfulness is both a literal and metaphorical force, shaping the characters' lives and the broader socio-political landscape of post-Arthurian Britain. Central to the novel is the pervasive mist that causes the people to forget their pasts, creating a world where collective memory is fragmented and history remains shrouded in ambiguity. This condition of amnesia serves as a key device through which Ishiguro explores the themes of trauma, reconciliation, and the moral complexities of memory. Forgetfulness, in the novel, is not simply a passive state of ignorance but a tool wielded by forces both human and supernatural to maintain peace and avoid confrontation with painful truths. By erasing memories of past conflicts, the mist prevents characters from addressing the sins of the past, creating a fragile peace that is built on the foundation of unspoken guilt and unresolved trauma. (Sim, 2016: 102-103)

The role of forgetfulness in *The Buried Giant* is multifaceted. On one level, it represents a form of spiritual amnesia, where individuals and entire communities are disconnected from their moral and historical roots. Axl and Beatrice, the central characters, are unable to fully remember their own past together, including key moments of betrayal and forgiveness. Their journey to recover these memories mirrors the larger quest for truth and reconciliation that reinforces the novel's plot. However, Ishiguro complicates the traditional narrative arc of memory retrieval by questioning whether remembering the past is always beneficial. Throughout the novel, characters grapple with the idea that certain memories, particularly those related to violence and betrayal, may be too painful to confront and that forgetfulness might offer a form of mercy. This tension between the desire to remember and the impulse to forget creates a narrative of moral ambiguity, where the line between justice and peace becomes blurred. (Wong, 2019: 88)

The figure of Sir Gawain, an aging knight tasked with protecting the mist of forgetfulness, embodies this paradox. He believes that the suppression of memory is necessary for the greater good, as it prevents the resurgence of old hatreds and the repetition of past violence. Yet, Wistan, a warrior from a different cultural background, insists that true peace can only be achieved through the recovery of memory and the acknowledgment of past wrongs. Their opposing views on forgetfulness reflect deeper questions about the role of memory in shaping both individual identities and collective histories. While Gawain represents the desire to protect a fragile peace built on forgetting, Wistan embodies the quest for justice through remembrance. The tension between these two characters highlights the moral complexity of the novel's exploration of

memory, as Ishiguro refuses to offer easy answers to the question of whether forgetting or remembering leads to true reconciliation. (Rothfork, 2021: 94)

From a missiological perspective, the theme of spiritual amnesia in *The Buried Giant* resonates with broader theological concerns about the nature of memory and its role in shaping faith and identity. In Christian theology, memory is often linked to the act of bearing witness to the truth of God's work in the world, both through the historical events of salvation history and through personal experiences of grace and transformation. Forgetfulness, by contrast, is associated with spiritual decay, a loss of connection to the divine narrative that shapes human existence. In this sense, the mist in *The Buried Giant* can be interpreted as a metaphor for the ways in which societies and individuals can become disconnected from their spiritual heritage, leading to a form of moral and theological amnesia. (Kirkham, 2020: 66)

The missiological implications of this spiritual amnesia are profound. In the novel, the characters' inability to remember their past sins prevents them from engaging in the processes of repentance, forgiveness, and reconciliation that are central to the Christian understanding of salvation. Without memory, there can be no true repentance, as individuals and communities remain unaware of the wrongs they have committed. Similarly, without the act of remembering, forgiveness becomes an abstract concept, disconnected from the specific actions and relationships that require healing. This raises important questions for missiology, particularly in the context of missionary work in cultures that have experienced historical trauma, colonization, or conflict. The missionary task often involves helping communities recover their collective memory, both in terms of their own cultural heritage and in relation to the broader narrative of God's work in history. (Lewis, 2021: 39)

Ishiguro's representation of forgetfulness as both a curse and a blessing complicates the traditional Christian narrative of memory as a pathway to redemption. In some cases, the novel suggests, forgetting may be necessary for survival, as remembering past traumas can lead to cycles of revenge and violence. This tension mirrors the missiological challenge of navigating the balance between memory and forgetfulness in contexts of historical injustice. Missionaries must grapple with the question of how to engage with communities that have experienced profound trauma, while also acknowledging the potential dangers of reopening old wounds. The process of healing, both spiritual and social, requires a delicate balance between remembering the past and moving forward into the future. *The Buried Giant* offers a poignant reflection on this dynamic, as characters struggle to find peace in a world where memory is both a burden and a gift. (Wells, 2016: 99)

Furthermore, the novel's depiction of forgetfulness as a tool of political control has important implications for understanding the relationship between power, memory, and faith in missiological contexts. In *The Buried Giant*, the mist of forgetfulness is maintained by those in power as a means of preventing conflict and maintaining social order. This raises important

questions about the ways in which memory can be manipulated or suppressed for political ends, both in secular and religious contexts. The role of the church, particularly in missionary work, often involves challenging such systems of control by bearing witness to the truth of the gospel, which calls for both remembrance and accountability. However, the book also warns of the potential dangers of a simplistic approach to memory, as the recovery of forgotten histories can lead to new conflicts if not accompanied by a spirit of forgiveness and reconciliation. (Shaffer, 2017: 53)

The missiological implications of *The Buried Giant* therefore extend beyond the individual characters' struggles with memory and forgetfulness, offering a broader commentary on the challenges of reconciliation in a world marked by historical trauma and moral ambiguity. The novel invites readers to reflect on the complexities of memory in the context of mission, where the proclamation of the gospel must be accompanied by a deep engagement with the histories and traumas of the communities being served. Ishiguro's exploration of spiritual amnesia, with its rich theological and moral undertones, provides a powerful lens through which to examine the role of memory in the missiological task, offering valuable insights for those engaged in the work of healing and reconciliation in a broken world. (De Lange, 2020: 183)

The Buried Giant provides a profound reflection on the role of forgetfulness in both personal and collective memory, raising important questions about the nature of forgiveness, justice, and peace. The novel's portrayal of spiritual amnesia offers a unique perspective on the missiological task, highlighting the challenges of engaging with communities that have experienced profound trauma and historical injustice. At the same time, Ishiguro's nuanced exploration of the moral complexities of memory and forgetfulness provides valuable insights for those engaged in the work of mission and reconciliation, offering a rich resource for theological reflection. (Olsen, 2018: 48)

III. Forgiveness and Reconciliation: The Unresolved Past

In *The Buried Giant*, Kazuo Ishiguro involvedly interlaces themes of memory, forgetfulness, and historical trauma, yet at its core, the novel wrestles with the elusive nature of forgiveness and reconciliation. These concepts, which shape the moral fabric of the narrative, unfold within a complex interplay of ethical dilemmas faced by the characters, especially as they confront the scars of their shared past. Forgiveness, in particular, appears as an ethical challenge rather than a straightforward resolution. As the protagonists attempt to reconcile their fractured memories, the unresolved past looms large, complicating any possibility of moral or emotional absolution. The relationship between Axl and Beatrice, as well as the broader history of conflict between the Britons and the Saxons, exemplifies the ethical ambiguities surrounding forgiveness, as the very act of remembering opens old wounds. In this sense, Ishiguro's novel can be read through a missiological lens, wherein the ethics of forgiveness reflect

the struggles of reconciliation within fractured communities of faith. (Annesley, 2017: 26)

The ethical complexity of forgiveness in Ishiguro's characters mirrors broader missiological concerns about reconciliation. Forgiveness, in the Christian tradition, is often presented as a moral imperative, yet in practice, it frequently entails navigating painful histories of violence, betrayal, and injustice. Axl, as a character embodying the weight of memory, struggles with the desire to forgive those who wronged him and his people, yet he is simultaneously burdened by the remnants of past betrayals that continue to haunt his relationship with Beatrice. This tension resonates with the writings of theologians like Miroslav Volf, particularly in *Exclusion and Embrace*, where Volf argues that forgiveness requires an acknowledgment of wrongdoing, even as it seeks to transcend the cycle of retribution. Like Axl, Volf's theological discourse points to the difficulty of embracing forgiveness when the wounds of the past remain raw. Ishiguro thus invites the reader to question whether true reconciliation is ever possible without first confronting the full scope of historical trauma. The ethical dilemma presented by the novel echoes a missiological tension found in the Christian mission itself, how can communities of faith preach forgiveness and reconciliation when unresolved histories of violence and exclusion persist?

The novel's representation of forgiveness is further complicated by the theme of forgetfulness, which Ishiguro presents as both a curse and a blessing. The characters' inability to remember the full extent of their past initially appears as a means of survival, a way to maintain peace between warring factions. However, as the mist of forgetfulness begins to lift, the characters are forced to confront the moral implications of their past actions. This dynamic raises profound ethical questions about the nature of reconciliation, particularly when the past remains unresolved. For instance, Beatrice's longing for reconciliation with Axl is fraught with uncertainty, as their fragmented memories obscure the full truth of their relationship. The novel's portrayal of forgiveness, in this sense, can be seen as a reflection of the broader challenges faced by missionary efforts to foster reconciliation in contexts marked by historical and intergenerational trauma. As theologian Dietrich Bonhoeffer suggests in *The Cost of Discipleship*, forgiveness often comes at a great personal cost, requiring not only a recognition of guilt but also a willingness to bear the burden of another's suffering. Ishiguro's characters, however, find themselves trapped in a liminal space where the cost of forgiveness is too high, and the past remains a haunting spectre. (Dietrich, 1959: 100)

In examining the ethics of forgiveness, it is essential to consider the role of power dynamics in the process of reconciliation. In *The Buried Giant*, the tension between the Britons and the Saxons reflects the unequal distribution of power and the resulting ethical dilemmas surrounding forgiveness. The novel suggests that forgiveness, when imposed from a position of dominance, risks perpetuating cycles of violence and oppression. This idea is echoed in the works of postcolonial theorists like Frantz Fanon, particularly in *The*

Wretched of the Earth, where Fanon critiques the notion of reconciliation as a form of pacification that often serves the interests of the oppressor rather than the oppressed. Ishiguro's narrative, while not explicitly post-colonial, engages with similar themes of historical memory and the ethics of reconciliation in the aftermath of conflict. The unresolved past, in this case, becomes a barrier to genuine forgiveness, as the power imbalances between the warring factions prevent the possibility of an equitable resolution. (Frantz, 1963: 77)

Resolution, in Ishiguro's novel, emerges as a troubled and incomplete process, one that mirrors the missiological challenges of nurturing peace in contexts marked by deep-seated divisions. The novel's depiction of the Britons and Saxons, who remain unable to fully reconcile their differences, reflects the broader difficulties of promoting reconciliation within fractured communities of faith. In the field of missiology, the dilemma of reconciliation often arises in the context of historical injustices, where the wounds of colonialism, violence, and exploitation continue to shape the dynamics of contemporary mission work. As theologian Andrew Walls notes in *The Cross-Cultural Process in Christian History*, reconciliation within missionary contexts requires not only the preaching of forgiveness but also an engagement with the historical realities that have contributed to divisions within the global church. In this sense, *The Buried Giant* offers a poignant reflection on the limits of reconciliation, as the characters' unresolved pasts prevent them from achieving the peace they so desperately seek. (Andrew, 2002: 125)

At the heart of the novel's exploration of reconciliation is the question of whether true forgiveness is possible in the face of historical trauma. Ishiguro's characters, like many in post-apartheid or post-genocide societies, struggle to reconcile their desire for peace with the lingering pain of past injustices. The novel's emphasis on memory and forgetfulness serves as a metaphor for the broader challenges faced by communities seeking reconciliation after periods of violence and oppression. In this regard, Ishiguro's work resonates with the writings of Desmond Tutu in *No Future Without Forgiveness*, where Tutu argues that reconciliation requires not only forgiveness but also the acknowledgment of past wrongs and the pursuit of restorative justice. Ishiguro, however, presents a more ambiguous picture, suggesting that the unresolved past may continue to haunt attempts at reconciliation, even when forgiveness is offered. (Tutu, 1999: 64)

The Buried Giant provides a profound exploration of the ethical dilemmas surrounding forgiveness and reconciliation, particularly in the context of unresolved historical trauma. The novel's illustration of characters grappling with their fragmented memories and the weight of past betrayals raises important questions about the nature of forgiveness and the possibility of reconciliation in fractured communities. Through its engagement with themes of memory, power, and historical trauma, the novel offers a profound reflection on the complexities of forgiveness, one that resonates with both theological and missiological concerns. Ishiguro's characters, like those in real-world contexts of conflict and division, find themselves caught between the desire

for peace and the haunting spectre of an unresolved past. As such, the novel serves as a powerful meditation on the ethical challenges of forgiveness, one that speaks to the broader dilemmas of reconciliation in both literary and missiological discourse. (Mathews, 2019: 80)

IV. Death and Afterlife: Missiological Perspectives on Mortality

Kazuo Ishiguro explores the theme of death in a way that is deeply intertwined with the novel's larger narrative of memory, forgetfulness, and reconciliation. The image of death in this novel moves beyond the mere cessation of life, inviting a deeper reflection on mortality, the afterlife, and the ethical dimensions of remembering and forgetting. As Axl and Beatrice journey through a mist-covered land, the looming presence of death accompanies them, not only as an existential reality but also as a force that shapes their relationship, their past, and the future they long to understand. In this context, death becomes a metaphor for the unknown, the mysterious boundary that separates the familiar world of the living from the enigmatic world beyond. Yet, death is also depicted as a space of potential resolution, a place where the unresolved tensions of the past might finally find clarity, whether through divine justice or spiritual reconciliation. (Kelleher, 2021: 147)

The interpretation of death in *The Buried Giant* is characterized by a haunting ambiguity, reflecting Ishiguro's broader narrative style that resists offering simple resolutions. Throughout the novel, the characters fight with the meaning of death not only as individuals but also as members of a post-war society where historical violence has been erased from collective memory. Axl and Beatrice, in their quest to resolve with their past and each other, confront the possibility of their own deaths, but this confrontation is laden with uncertainty. The figure of the boatman, who ferries souls to an afterlife shrouded in myth and speculation, symbolizes the ambiguity surrounding death and its aftermath in the novel. Unlike traditional representations of death as a clearly defined event leading to an eternal afterlife, the boatman's role in *The Buried Giant* evokes a liminal space between life and death, where the past remains unresolved and the future unknowable. The characters' encounter with the boatman emphasizes that death is not simply an end but part of an ongoing journey, one that challenges the boundaries between memory, identity, and eternity. (Bradbury, 2017: 106)

The characters' uncertainty about their own fate after death reflects the broader existential questions that arise in the face of mortality. Thus, *The Buried Giant* not only reflects on the human fear of death but also engages with Christian conceptions of the afterlife, juxtaposing the clarity of theological doctrine with the ambiguity of lived experience. (Davidson, 2019: 274)

In the Christian tradition, death and the afterlife have been central concerns, particularly in relation to the missional imperative of proclaiming the gospel of eternal life. Christian views on mortality emphasize the resurrection of the body and the promise of eternal life in Christ, as articulated in the writings of Paul, especially in *1 Corinthians 15*. The resurrection doctrine affirms that death has been conquered through Christ's

victory, and believers can look forward to a future where death no longer holds power over human existence. However, the representation of death in *The Buried Giant* challenges the simplicity of this theological assurance, as the characters face a reality where the past is fragmented and the future uncertain. The novel's depiction of death as a journey toward an unknown afterlife mirrors the existential anxieties that often accompany discussions of mortality, even within a Christian framework. While Christian theology offers hope for eternal life, Ishiguro's narrative asks whether that hope can be fully grasped in a world where memory, identity, and relationships are in flux. (Pateman, 2016: 144)

This tension between the theological promise of eternal life and the existential uncertainty surrounding death is central to missiological discussions of mortality. For missionaries, the proclamation of the gospel is often framed as a message of hope in the face of death, offering the promise of resurrection and eternal communion with God. Yet, as *The Buried Giant* illustrates, the human experience of death is often more complex and fraught with ambiguity than simple theological affirmations might suggest. Death as a mysterious and unresolved reality summons reflection on how missionaries engage with communities where death is experienced not only as a spiritual transition but also as a social, cultural, and historical phenomenon. The unresolved nature of death in Ishiguro's narrative challenges missionaries to grapple with the ethical dimensions of mortality, particularly in contexts marked by historical trauma, cultural dislocation, and the collective forgetting of past violence. In this way, *The Buried Giant* offers a profound reflection on the missiological implications of mortality, urging a deeper engagement with the complexities of death and its significance in both individual and communal life. (D'Addario, 2021: 75)

Christian views on death and eternal life are extremely entrenched in the biblical narrative, where the themes of mortality, resurrection, and judgment play central roles. The Book of Revelation, for instance, offers a vision of the ultimate defeat of death and the establishment of a new heaven and earth, where death will be no more and God's people will live in eternal communion with Him. Yet, this eschatological hope is accompanied by the reality of judgment, where the dead are held accountable for their actions. In *The Buried Giant*, the boatman's role in determining who is worthy to cross to the afterlife echoes the Christian idea of judgment, though in a far more ambiguous and morally complex way. The boatman's decision is based not on theological criteria but on the characters' memory of their past actions, raising questions about the nature of forgiveness, reconciliation, and justice. In this sense, Ishiguro's representation of death complicates the Christian doctrine of judgment, suggesting that the past, particularly when forgotten or repressed, plays a significant role in shaping one's fate in the afterlife. (Toker, 2022: 292)

It resonates with comprehensive philosophical reflections on mortality, particularly in existentialist thought. For thinkers like Martin Heidegger, death rep-

resents the ultimate horizon of human existence, a fundamental aspect of being that shapes one's understanding of life. In *Being and Time*, Heidegger argues that the awareness of death forces individuals to confront the meaning of their existence, highlighting the existential significance of mortality. Similarly, in *The Buried Giant*, death functions as a central concern for Axl and Beatrice, shaping their quest for reconciliation and their understanding of the past. The uncertainty surrounding their future, particularly in relation to death, mirrors the existential anxieties that arise in the face of mortality. Yet, unlike Heidegger's emphasis on individual confrontation with death, Ishiguro's characters face death within the context of their relationship and their broader social world, suggesting that mortality is not only an individual concern but also a communal and relational one. This relational aspect of death is significant from a missiological perspective, as it highlights the importance of community, memory, and reconciliation in the face of mortality. (Heidegger, 1962: 37)

From a Christian missiological perspective, the communal dimension of death is particularly important, as the hope of eternal life is not simply an individual promise but a collective one, grounded in the belief in the resurrection of the body and the renewal of all creation. The doctrine of the communion of saints, for example, emphasizes the interconnectedness of believers, both living and dead, in the body of Christ. In *The Buried Giant*, however, the communal aspect of death is complicated by the characters' experience of forgetfulness and fragmentation. The mist that covers the land erases not only individual memories but also the collective memory of past violence, disrupting the sense of community and shared history. This disruption of memory and community in relation to death raises important questions for missiological engagement with mortality, particularly in contexts where historical trauma and cultural dislocation have fractured communal bonds. Ishiguro's narrative thus invites reflection on how Christian theology can address the complexities of death in a world marked by memory loss, historical violence, and the fragmentation of relationships. (Williams, 2015: 117)

The representation of death in *The Buried Giant* challenges traditional Christian views on mortality and the afterlife, offering a more ambiguous and morally complex vision of what lies beyond death. Through the figure of the boatman and the characters' journey toward an unknown afterlife, Ishiguro invites readers to reflect on the unresolved tensions between memory, forgiveness, and justice that shape one's fate in death. This ambiguity resonates with missiological reflections on mortality, where the proclamation of eternal life must grapple with the complexities of human experience, historical trauma, and cultural diversity. At the same time, the Christian hope of resurrection and eternal communion with God offers a counterpoint to the uncertainty depicted in the novel, affirming that death is not the end but the beginning of a new form of life in Christ. Thus, *The Buried Giant* serves as a profound reflection on the missiological implications of death, offering a narrative that both challenges and enriches

Christian understandings of mortality and the afterlife. (Robbins, 2020: 152)

Conclusion

From a missiological perspective, *The Buried Giant* offers profound insights into the nature of Christian mission, particularly in contexts marked by historical trauma, cultural dislocation, and spiritual ambiguity. The novel's depiction of a world shaped by forgetfulness, where the past has been obscured by a literal and figurative mist, invites reflection on the role of memory and history in shaping missionary engagement with communities. In Christian theology, mission is often understood as a call to bring the gospel of reconciliation, healing, and renewal to a broken world. Yet, as Ishiguro's narrative suggests, this task is fraught with complexities, particularly in societies where collective memory has been fractured by violence and repression. The novel's portrayal of a post-war Britain, haunted by the unresolved tensions of its violent past, mirrors the missiological challenge of engaging with communities that have experienced historical trauma. The erasure of memory, while initially appearing as a form of peace, ultimately prevents true reconciliation, as the characters must confront the buried truths of their past in order to move forward.

Finally, Ishiguro's exploration of mortality and the afterlife in *The Buried Giant* provides a rich source of missiological reflection on the Christian hope of resurrection and eternal life. Throughout the novel, the characters' confrontation with death, both individually and collectively, serves as a metaphor for the larger existential questions that underlie human existence. For Axl and Beatrice, their journey toward the afterlife is fraught with uncertainty, as they grapple with the possibility of being separated after death and the unknown nature of what lies beyond. This portrayal of death as a space of both fear and hope mirrors the Christian theological understanding of death as both an end and a beginning. Missiologically, this theme invites reflection on how missionaries engage with questions of mortality and the afterlife in their proclamation of the gospel. The Christian message of resurrection offers hope in the face of death, but Ishiguro's narrative reminds readers that this hope must be communicated in ways that acknowledge the deep existential anxieties that accompany human mortality. Thus, *The Buried Giant* provides a profound meditation on the complexities of faith, doubt, and mission in a world marked by uncertainty, ambiguity, and the search for meaning.

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